

Validator selection in proof-of-vote

Assigning each person a unique identifier incrementally from 1, validators are selected by randomly selecting a voter, $1 + \text{randomNumber}/(\text{maxHash}/\text{getPopulation}())$. The voters are analogous to individual miners in a mining pool, and the validator the mining pool.

The randomness is provided by validators as they produce blocks, using a simple hash onion, $\text{randomNumber}^{\wedge} = \text{hashOnion}[\text{validator}].\text{pop}()$. Validators pre-commit n hashes, preventing any collusion attacks on the random number generation.

